

ORTHO-SUBSTITUTED DIPHENYLS. PART V

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The methyl ester, ethyl ester, the chloride and the amide of *o*-phenylcinnamic acid have been prepared. *o*-Phenylstyrene has been obtained from *o*-phenylbromostyrene with the intermediate formation of the magnesium compound of *o*-phenylbromostyrene.

It has now been possible to prepare a number of derivatives of *o*-phenylcinnamic acid whose preparation has already been described (Zaheer and Faseeh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 381). The methyl and ethyl esters have been obtained with concentrated H_2SO_4 as the condensing agent in both cases by the method used by Fisher and Spier (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 3254) to prepare the corresponding ethyl ester of cinnamic acid. With thionyl chloride as the chlorinating agent, *o*-phenylcinnamoyl chloride has been prepared in almost theoretical yield. With cinnamic acid and thionyl chloride, an almost theoretical yield of cinnamoyl chloride also was obtained. The amide has also been prepared from *o*-phenylcinnamoyl chloride in the usual manner.

It was also attempted to prepare indone and phenylindone from cinnamic acid and *o*-phenylcinnamoyl chloride respectively by means of a ring-closure through an internal condensation by the removal of the elements of hydrochloric acid with the agency of aluminium chloride or zinc chloride. Fittig and Erdmann (*Annalen*, 1883, 216, 179) have, however, already noted the failure of cinnamic acid to yield indone by treating with conc. H_2SO_4 . Roser (*Annalen*, 1888, 247, 129) suggested that stereochemical isomerism of these compounds might be responsible for this failure to ring-closure, while at the same time certain substituted products e. g., phenyldichloro-acrylic acid (Zincke *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1269) and phenyldibromo-acrylic acid (Roser, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1273) have been successfully made to yield the corresponding dihalogeno derivatives of indone. Support to Roser's view was lent by the subsequent preparation by Kipping (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 56, 484) and Braun and Manz (*Annalen*, 1929, 468, 276) of hydrindone and *o*-phenylhydrindone by the action of aluminium chloride on phenylpropionyl chloride and *o*-diphenylpropionyl chloride respectively, where obviously there could be no possibilities of stereochemical isomerism. This observation has been confirmed again by the present

authors who also failed to obtain indone from cinnamoyl chloride. In the case of *o*-phenylcinnamoyl chloride, however, a small yield of a crystalline product (m.p. 242°) was obtained. Both the chlorides gave large quantities of unidentified polymerised products.

The identification of the crystalline product obtained from *o*-phenylcinnamoyl chloride and other products of these reaction awaits further investigation.

The usual method for the preparation of styrene is to distill cinnamic acid in presence of quinol ("Organic Syntheses", 1928, VIII, p. 85; Higginbottom, "Reactions of Organic Compounds", p. 206). The yields, however, are not good. Another method for the preparation of styrene has been described by Rupe and Proske (*Ber.*, 1910, 43, 1232) by the action of ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid on the magnesium compound of ω -bromostyrene, when 55% yield of styrene along with 20% of 1:4-diphenylbutadiene (m.p. 147-48°) were obtained. By adopting Rupe and Proske's method it has now been possible to obtain *o*-phenylstyrene by the decomposition of the magnesium compound of *o*-phenyl- ω -bromostyrene, whose preparation has already been reported (Zaheer *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 57). The yield obtained (57%) is quite satisfactory and very much better than the 24% yield obtained by Bradsher and Wert (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2806) by dehydration through heating for an hour at 160° with potassium bisulphate of the secondary alcohol obtained by the interaction of the magnesium derivative of 2-iododiphenyl with acetaldehyde, but not as good as the 70% yield reported very recently to have been obtained by Huber, Renoll, Rossow and Moury (*ibid.*, 1946, 68, 1111) by the vapour phase dehydration of the same secondary alcohol. In addition to the *o*-phenylstyrene obtained as an oil boiling at 126-29°/3-5mm, a higher boiling point fraction which gave a crystalline solid (m.p. 86-88°) was also obtained in a 9% yield. This has not yet been fully identified but is probably the tetraphenylbutadiene corresponding to diphenylbutadiene obtained by Rupe and Proske (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl Ester of o-Phenylcinnamic Acid.—Absolute methyl alcohol (14g., 10 mol.) was mixed with pure concentrated sulphuric acid (2.2 g., 0.5 mol.) and *o*-phenylcinnamic acid (10g., 1 mol.) gradually added. The ethereal extract of the ester obtained after the usual treatment was dried overnight on anhydrous sodium sulphate.

The ether was distilled off and the residue on distillation under reduced pressure gave a viscous oil, b.p. $184^{\circ}/4\text{mm.}$, yield 8.6 g. (81%). (Found : C, 80.80 ; H, 5.47. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 80.67 ; H 5.88 per cent).

Ethyl ester of o-phenylcinnamic acid, obtained in a method as above, gave a colourless viscous oil, b.p. $195^{\circ}/4\text{mm.}$, yield 9.5 g. (84%). (Found : C, 81.23 ; H, 6.11. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 80.95 ; H, 6.35 per cent).

o-Phenylcinnamoyl Chloride.—*o*-Phenylcinnamic acid (10 g., 1 mol.) was taken in a round flask and thionyl chloride (6g., 1 mol.) added to it carefully. As on mixing, acid fumes (HCl and SO_2) were evolved, the reaction was carried out in a fume chamber. An intense cooling effect was produced on mixing the acid with the thionyl chloride and it persisted till the completion of the reaction. At the end of the completion of the reaction (2 hours) the solution was refluxed for 20 minutes on the water-bath and then the condenser was removed and the mixture heated for further 10 minutes, and distilled under filter pump up to a temperature of 225° to remove all excess of thionyl chloride. Final distillation under reduced pressure gave a highly viscous, colourless, liquid, b. p. $182^{\circ}/3\text{mm.}$ which solidified on cooling yield 9 g. (83%). (Found : Cl, 14.51. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{OCl}$ requires Cl, 14.64 per cent).

o-Phenylcinnamamide.—*o*-Phenylcinnamoyl chloride was melted in warm water and added in drops to an excess of a concentrated aqueous solution of ammonia when fumes were produced and a white solid separated. The solid was well broken and thoroughly stirred with a glass rod, and left overnight. The contents were filtered, well washed with cold water and finally crystallised from hot water, m. p. $163\text{--}64^{\circ}$, yield quantitative. (Found : C, 80.83 ; H, 5.68 ; N, 6.24. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{ON}$ requires C, 80.72 ; H, 5.83 ; N, 6.28 per cent).

Magnesium Compound of o-Phenylbromostyrene.—A solution of *o*-phenyl-*o*-bromostyrene (10 g., 1 mol.) in absolute ether (50 c. c.) was gradually added to magnesium flakes (1.1 g., 1 mol.) covered with absolute ether (50 c. c.). A particle of iodine was added and the air was replaced by nitrogen. The contents were gradually warmed up to 45° and were continually stirred and refluxed. Within 15 minutes, the colour due to iodine started disappearing and with the gradual disappearance of magnesium flakes, the solution became turbid and thick within another 30 minutes. At the end of two hours, during which stirring and refluxing were continued and the temperature maintained at 45° , no more particles of magnesium were found to disappear and the reaction was assumed to be completed. The solution was made up to

100 c. c. with absolute ether and a 10 c. c. portion was hydrolysed by boiling with 150 c. c. of water and 20 c. c. of standard sulphuric acid. The excess of acid was titrated against standard sodium hydroxide according to the method described by Gilman and Meyer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 159). The quantity of the magnesium compound produced was nearly 80% of the theory.

o-Phenylstyrene.—An ethereal solution of the magnesium compound of *o*-phenyl-*o*-bromostyrene (10g., 1 mol.) was prepared as described above. Then an excess of ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid (15%) was added to the solution, which was then well shaken for half an hour, at the end of which it reacted acid to litmus. The solution was then extracted with ether, and the ethereal solution dried overnight over fused calcium chloride. The ether was distilled off and the residue on distillation under reduced pressure gave a colourless oil, b. p. 126-29°/3-5 mm., the yield being 4.1g. (57%). (Found: C 93.45; H, 6.21. $C_{14}H_{12}$ requires C, 93.33; H, 6.67 per cent).

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